

ISSUES OF FAMILY AND MARRIAGE IN THE TEACHINGS OF EASTERN
THINKERS

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Abstract: *This scientific article provides theoretical information about the Family and its values by Eastern thinkers. In the East, special attention is paid to the issue of family upbringing, the family duties of husband and wife, and the role of women in the strength of the family. Information is provided about moral upbringing, which is of particular importance in raising girls. The characteristics of women in the family are highlighted.*

Keywords: *family, marriage, values, upbringing, family relations, society, child upbringing, moral upbringing*

Аннотация: *В данной научной статье представлены теоретические сведения о семье и ее ценностях восточными мыслителями. На Востоке особое внимание уделяется вопросу семейного воспитания, семейным обязанностям мужа и жены, роли женщины в стабильности семьи. Показаны сведения о нравственном воспитании, которое имеет особое значение в воспитании девочек. Выделены особенности женщины в семье.*

Ключевые слова: *семья, брак, ценности, образование, семейные отношения, общество, воспитание детей, нравственное воспитание.*

Introduction. Family is considered a sacred sanctuary. The concept of family is a small society based on the union of spouses, kinship ties, mutual relations between husband and wife, parents and children, brothers and sisters, grandparents and other relatives who manage a common household. Family life is characterized by material and spiritual processes, and its role in the development of the child is invaluable. In this sense, the most valuable traditions: honesty, truthfulness, good upbringing, honor,

modesty, kindness, diligence - all these human qualities are formed, first of all, in the family. The family, having a strong influence on the life of society, performs a number of functions: giving birth to children, working in the household, managing the household, satisfying the physical needs of family members, educating the younger generation, influencing their spiritual and moral development.

Family is a sacred homeland. In the family, special attention is paid to the purity of offspring. Family includes three aspects - marriage, care for family property, and raising children. Family is based on purity and cleanliness, mutual love, loyalty and devotion. Only when the family is strong, peaceful, prosperous, and healthy can there be stability in society. Its strength depends on peace and tranquility in the family, sincere relationships with each other, and the moral upbringing of family members. It is known that family moral values are the main criterion in the formation of upbringing. In this process, it is advisable for the activities of the family, school, mahalla, and public organizations to work in harmony.

Purpose and its justification. The importance of family relationships, the influence of the family on social and spiritual development, as well as the role of upbringing in the family in human life. The article pays special attention to such issues as raising children, moral and spiritual values, as well as spousal relations. The development and strength of the family are important for the well-being and stability of society. The ideas expressed in it include the views of thinkers, historical figures, and scholars on family issues, which contribute to the revival of modern family values and traditions.

The main conclusion of the article is that the family is the main component of society, its stability and strength are ensured through mutual love, respect, and proper fulfillment of duties by family members. Morality and upbringing carried out in the family, as well as family relations, shape the political, social, and spiritual order in society. It is known that family upbringing determines the behavior of each person, social relations, as well as the striving for a prosperous and peaceful life.

Description and solution of the scientific problem. The article focuses on the views of many thinkers and historical figures in the field of family relations and family upbringing to determine the description and solution of the scientific problem. The scientific problem in the sphere of family relations is focused on the relationships between family members, the moral and spiritual aspects of upbringing, as well as the role and significance of the family institution in society. The importance of family relationships and upbringing: Family relationships are a fundamental component of society. The relationships between family members, especially between spouses, parents, and children, influence social and moral norms in society. The process of upbringing in the family lays the foundation for the spiritual and moral development of

children. Solutions to this depend on the proper organization of family behavior, moral values, and family upbringing. Legal and ethical foundations of family relations: Legal and ethical criteria of family relations are important for solving the scientific problem. The alignment of officials, spiritual teachings, and social work is crucial for strengthening family relationships. For this, the rights and obligations of family members, especially the responsibilities of parents towards their children, must be defined. Views of thinkers and scholars on the family: Ideas about family relations, upbringing, and family traditions are of great importance in solving the main problems of family life. Responsible thinkers, such as Abu Ali ibn Sina, Yusuf Khas Hajib, Alisher Navoi, Amir Temur, and others, expressed valuable thoughts about the importance of family life, morality, and virtues in family relationships. Their views contribute to the improvement and strengthening of family relationships and the following solutions:

1. Intensification of work on family upbringing and the widespread introduction of moral, spiritual, and psychological rules for the effective resolution of trust, needs, and problems among family members.

2. Clear and understandable communication of family duties and responsibilities to parents, as well as further strengthening the role of family members in the spiritual and moral development of children.

3. Preservation of family values in society and the introduction of attitudes towards family issues into the social system.

4. Development of scientific research in the field of family relations and arousing interest in working together in order for each member to correctly fulfill their duties in practice. These descriptions and solutions are aimed at ensuring the stability of family upbringing and relationships.

One of the thinkers who is distinguished by his remarkable views on family relations is Abu Ali ibn Sina. The scholar's valuable thoughts, especially about how women should be in life, never lose their significance. In his work "Tadbiri manzil", in the section "Afsofiy behtar in zanho", it is said that women should have good behavior, and in this work it is emphasized that women should have the following characteristics:

1. Let them be knowledgeable.
2. He must believe in religion.
3. Be shy and modest.
4. Be courageous by nature.
5. She must deeply love her husband.
6. Think about childbirth and child-rearing.
7. Don't be talkative.
8. She should be obedient to her husband.

9. Be honest, humble, and wise.
10. He should never tarnish his honor.
11. She must be careful with her husband, show him proper respect, and be polite.
12. He knows his duties well.
13. A wife should know how to use household items correctly and economically.
14. She should eliminate the shortcomings in her husband through her nature and good qualities.”¹

A woman who embodies these qualities will certainly be happy and her family will live a prosperous life.

The book “Kutadgu Bilig” (“Knowledge Leading to Happiness”), written by the great thinker of the 11th century Yusuf Khas Hajib, reflects comprehensive views and teachings on science and enlightenment, ethics, state governance, family and family relations. According to him, the greatest happiness for a person is having a child and raising them. Raising a child places a great responsibility on every parent. The scholar emphasizes in his work that parents, especially fathers, should pay attention to child-rearing in the family, saying: “When a father supervises and teaches (various crafts) to raise his child, when they grow up, he rejoices saying he has a son and daughter”. ²The work widely emphasizes that raising children well is both a duty and an obligation of every parent.

The work provides valuable insights into the qualities and virtues that should be considered when choosing a spouse, the role, place, and significance of personal qualities and virtues in managing family life, the norms of marital relationships, and the important conditions for a prosperous life³.

Our great ancestor, the commander Amir Timur, paid as much serious attention to family matters as to state affairs. Sahibkiran, in particular, expressed the following thoughts about the choice of a bride: “In the anxiety of marrying off my sons, grandsons, and relatives, I paid attention to the search for a bride”.

Our great ancestor, the commander Amir Timur, paid as much serious attention to family matters as to state affairs. Sahibkiran, in particular, expressed the following thoughts about the choice of a bride: “In the anxiety of marrying off my sons, grandsons, and relatives, I paid attention to the search for a bride. I considered this work equivalent to government work. I inquired about the bride's lineage, her seven generations. Through special people, I determined his health and physical development. I gave a grand wedding and brought a bride to the people only if she had her lineage, manners, health

¹ Rahimov S. Abu Ali ibn Sino ta'lim va tarbiya haqida [On Education and Upbringing According to Abu Ali Ibn Sina]. Tashkent: O'qituvchi, 1967. p. 99.

² Yusuf Khos Khajib. Qutadghu Bilig [The Wisdom of Royal Glory]. Tashkent, 1989. p. 97

³ Yusuf Khos Khajib. Qutadghu Bilig [The Wisdom of Royal Glory]. Tashkent: Yulduzcha, 1990. p. 192

and strength, and was free from all flaws”⁴. These views demonstrate Amir Temur's responsibility to society in family and social relations of that time and important points in the upbringing of future generations. His firmness and teachings in this area emphasize that he did not associate the people with very large celebrations, but considered not only the social status of women, but also the general well-being of the population. Through this, it is important to study Amir Temur's philosophical and practical approach to family issues.

The views of the great scholar Alisher Navoi on marital relations, duties, virtues of women, and their place in the family are incomparable. In the chapter “On Marriage and Wives” of the work “Mahbub-ul-qulub”, the thinker expressed wonderful thoughts about marriage and its benefits, family etiquette, and the virtues of women in the family. Navoi discusses the role of women in life as follows: “A good wife is the wealth and happiness of the family. The cleanliness of the house depends on it, the peace and tranquility of the homeowner depends on it”⁵ Through these thoughts, we can see the advice that should be specifically followed in raising daughters. Of course, we must follow these recommendations in our daily lives, considering them important factors in raising daughters.

In particular, one of the Eastern thinkers who lived and worked in the second half of the 19th century, Ahmad Donish, in his work “Navodir ulvaqoe” (“Rare Events”), described in detail “Description of Marriage Etiquette, Marriage Conditions, Enmity between Mother-in-Law and Daughter-in-Law”. According to the thinker, when a person reaches a certain age, the need for marriage arises. Of course, during this period, a person gains an understanding of family, family happiness, marital relations, childhood, and parental duties. Indeed, the wise man says that it is the duty of every man (husband) to love and respect a woman. Family happiness is achieving people's dreams, desires, and goals. Ahmad Donish explains the idea that family happiness depends more on women, because there is no greater blessing for a man than a righteous wife, and that harmony, peace, and order in the family are in their hands, as well as the motives for creating a family⁶.

Eastern thinkers of the middle of the 19th century took a strict and systematic approach, especially to the issue of the family. Ahmad Donish's connection of family happiness in marital relations, especially with the role of women, deserves special attention. According to him, a woman's piety and pleasant and respectful relationships with women are the main conditions for harmony and order in the family. Here, the husband's responsibility and respect for the woman are highlighted, as, according to

⁴ Ayol – muqaddassan [Woman is Sacred]. Tashkent: Yozuvchi, 1999. p. 242.

⁵ Alisher Navoi. Mahbub-ul-Qulub [Beloved of the Hearts]. Tashkent, 1966. Vol. 13. p. 244

⁶ Ahmad Donish. Navodir ul-vaqoe' [Rare Events]. Dushanbe: Donish, 1989. p. 339.

Donish, a woman's well-being and health influence the overall state and happiness of the family. Ahmad Donish's connection of family happiness to the character and qualities of a woman, his views on the influence of righteous and especially harmonious helpful women on family development in his time, shows that they are deeply connected with the social and cultural environment of that time. Therefore, to achieve peace and stability in the family, it is necessary to maintain a high level of relationships and morality on both sides, especially between women.

One of the great representatives of the Turkestan Jadid movement of the 20th century, Abdurauf Fitrat, pays special attention to the issue of the family and its place in the life of society. In the scholar's work "Family or Family Management Procedures", everything from the necessity of creating a family to the relationships between family members, the rights and duties of parents and children, and his views on child-rearing are deeply illuminated. In this work, the sage puts forward valuable thoughts about marriage and what the future spouse should pay attention to first and foremost. The writer's valuable thoughts on what kind of wife to choose when it is necessary to marry, what the mahr and wedding should be like, how spouses should live, the rights of parents, and the education of daughters deserve attention⁷. Abdurauf Fitrat emphasizes the importance of moral education in the family for society as well, in this work he shows the necessity of health, sound thinking and morality for a person to achieve perfection, and also provides information about the Sharia rulings related to the birth of a child in the family in the second chapter of this work, entitled "Child Upbringing"⁸. In this work, it is highlighted that if the population decreases, it will definitely disappear completely in the world, which tribe does not want to disappear, it should strive to increase the population, first of all, to preserve the child in the womb, and not to allow infants to suffer from various diseases, and Muslims should focus all their efforts on the protection of their descendants.

Conclusion: The conclusion from the thoughts of our scholars is that it is desirable for women to have not only external and internal beauty, but also a perfect moral image. This, in turn, is directly related to upbringing in the family. Many aspects of upbringing are directly related to the moral maturity of parents, the warmth of their relationship, and the psychological environment in the family. Because the moral character of parents plays an important role in upbringing. Also, the role of moral and ethical education carried out in the family is enormous in raising spiritually mature, physically healthy children. The traditions and values of our people in the field of moral

⁷ Fitrat A. Oila yoki oila boshqarish tartiblari [Family or the Rules of Family Management]. Tashkent: Ma'naviyat, 1998. p. 8

⁸ Fitrat A. Oila yoki oila boshqarish tartiblari [Family or the Rules of Family Management]. Translated and annotated by Sh. Vohidov; edited by H. Boltaboyev. Tashkent: Cho'lpon Publishing House, 2013. p. 144.

education have been formed and developed over the centuries. Pre-Islamic moral values, Islamic traditions, wise sayings of great thinkers, rituals expressed in oral folk art, customs, rules of conduct and conduct were the basis for moral and ethical education in the family. In the process of studying the research of the above-mentioned Eastern thinkers on family and upbringing, we can come to the following conclusions. The family is an important component of society. The formation and development of the family was directly related to the political, economic, social, and spiritual relations in the life of society. Changes in the life of society, people's lifestyle, living and working conditions, national moral norms, psychology, religious beliefs also influenced the moral, legal, and social criteria of family relations.

When studying socio-demographic research devoted to the problem of the family, the legal and moral foundations of family relations, the duty of parents to society and their children have always been at the center of attention of scientists. They also emphasized that young people should understand that family is a great spirituality, value, duty and responsibility, and that young men and women should have a complete and correct understanding of our national traditions and values in forming a strong family from a young age. Because family life and the relationship between parents are also the main conditions for the formation of such concepts and ideas. In the works of Eastern scholars, the issues of marriage and the choice of a bride have always been in the center of attention, since in different periods of history, brides were recognized as the successors of generations.

Such thinkers as Abu Ali ibn Sina, Yusuf Khas Hajib, Amir Temur, Alisher Navoi, Ahmad Donish, and Abdurauf Fitrat, having improved their theories about the family, paid special attention to the role of women, marital relations, and the importance of raising children. They emphasized not only inner beauty, but also the achievement of moral perfection as an important factor of family upbringing. Norms, morals, and values in the family are the basis of the harmonious process of upbringing and are an important factor for the future of society.

The strength of family relationships is based on effective and unconditional trust, mutual respect, and contributions between each member. The psychological environment in the family, spiritual maturity, and moral values play a key role in the stability and well-being of society. As a result, noble views on the family and the importance of modern upbringing are the most effective basis for the younger generation to achieve a healthy life and spiritual maturity. The family is the main system for the peace and well-being of society, and each member should correctly feel their virtues and duties in family relations.

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